

A Research-based approach in finding the Correlation between Scientific Principles stated by Vedic Period Rishis and Modern Scientists

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ABSTRACT:

In this paper, a discussion has been carried out on some very valuable scientific theory and principles implemented by Indian Ancient Rishis and Munis which was later discovered by scientists. Some of these include atomic theory, principles of motions, battery generation techniques, Ayurveda, plant science, surgery, the theory of gravity, aerospace, the invention of zero, pi, theory of relativity and time, Sphericity of earth, the architectural concept in the Vedas, and motion of the earth, Chemical Engineering, Military based instruments, etc. discussed during Vedic period. Again a strong, short, and pointed correlation has been established between these scientific principles, theories with modern inventions. This paper also states how current modern laws and principles have already been stated and explained during the Indian Vedic period in the form of Sanskrit shloka and Upanishad in well-explained and logical manners that were used and credits given to other country scientists. The objective of this paper is to conveying information on the advanced technology implementation which was existed during the Indian Vedic period before long years ago and which was adopted all over the rest of the world later we accepted. The authors are also trying to convey the information related to the least negative effects of Vedic technology for living beings, earth, and atmosphere. Here, an attempt has been made for dragging out the versatility and uniquely identifiability of Indian Vedic science and technology in front of the world which is the main motto of this paper.

Keywords: Acharya Kanad, Agastya Samhita, Aryabhatta, Charak, Vimana, Shakuna Vimana, Bhardwaj, Vastu Sastra, Dragon 1

1. INTRODUCTION

Indians said that the first aircraft was made by Indians but others laughed. Indian Veda said that they discovered the solar system was round while the western scientists were busy claiming that the earth was flat. But now, the people who laughed at Indians are agreeing that India is the hub of knowledge. Western scientists accepted that Veda is full of knowledge. When the Universities of Manchester and Exeter team researched Veda, they found that Veda had passed on their knowledge to Jesuit missionaries during their visit to India in the fifteenth century which is then was passed on to Isaac Newton eventually[1]. Some principles which were claimed/invented by a different scientist, physicist and for which these scientists, physics feeling proud, taking so many credits have already mentioned and explained very elaborately in Veda since long years ago. This is not just a guess or not a flying statement; this is facts that are not easily digesting by many people in the world now. Vedic Science, Some facts, theories, principles, and laws of the modern period and their correlation with Indian Vedic periods have been discussed in the next sections.

2. VEDIC SCIENCE

The name "Vedic Science" thus indicates both the ancient traditional origins of this body of knowledge and the modern commitment to experience, system, testability, and the demand that knowledge is useful in improving the quality of human life.